

Examining the Digital Landscape: Identifying the Key Factors Influencing the Preference For Digital Newspapers in Agra

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the key factors influencing preference for digital newspapers in Agra, India. A large-scale structured data collection was conducted to examine the key determinants shaping the choice of digital newspapers over traditional formats. A Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was employed to identify the factors that influence the preferences of respondents. Four key factors were identified as influencing preferences: (1) visual content (images, infographics), (2) interactive content (quizzes, polls), (3) long-form features and in-depth analysis, and (4) user-generated content (comments, discussions). Reliability analysis resulted in a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.787, indicating good internal consistency among the items on the measurement instrument. The results of this study provide valuable insights into the consumption of news in digital versus print formats within the specified community. However, as more readers appear to go online, questions naturally arise about the role of content as a determinant of newspaper choice, especially now that publishers earnestly seek a better business model to sustain the already troubled print industry.

Keywords Digital Newspaper, Agra, Engagement Patterns, Customer Satisfaction.

Introduction

Like soap operas, newspapers are a media form characterized by a combination of content and delivery platform, this platform, for newspapers, initially being print but now also including digital editions. Also like soap operas, newspapers have been negatively affected by changes in audience behavior, with falls in the circulation of their printed editions as consumers have invested more of their finite attention in other media, such as television and the internet. (Thurman & Fletcher, 2019).

In response to rapid technological advancements, E-newspapers emerged as digital versions of traditional newspapers. Technological factors such as the growth of the internet, improvements in connectivity, and the advent of mobile devices contributed to the evolution of E-newspapers. These platforms offer enhanced accessibility, convenience, and interactive features, catering to the changing preferences of modern consumers. (Matt, 2023)

Research Questions

RQ1. What are the key demographic, technological, and content-related factors influencing the Preference for Digital Newspapers in Agra?

RQ2. What is the Consumer Satisfaction level with digital newspapers and their engagement patterns Engagement in Agra?

Objective of study

Understanding the factors that influence individuals' preferences for digital newspapers is crucial in the rapidly evolving media landscape. This study aims to investigate the key determinants shaping the choice of digital newspapers over traditional formats. Identifying these factors can provide valuable insights into consumer behavior, enabling media outlets and advertisers to tailor their strategies effectively. The study addresses the following aspects:

1. Demographic Factors: Exploring how age, educational qualification, income, gender, occupation, and geographic region may impact individuals' preferences for digital newspapers.

2. Qualitative Factors: Investigating subjective aspects such as readability, user experience, and content relevance that may contribute to the selection of digital newspapers.

3. Technological Awareness: Analyzing the influence of individuals' awareness of technological advancements and their ability to access and engage with digital content.

4. Time Considerations: Examining how time constraints and the convenience of accessing digital newspapers at any time may impact the choice of this media

Research Objectives

RO1. To Identify demographic, technological, and content-related factors influencing the Preference for Digital Newspapers in Agra.

RO2. To Examine Consumer Satisfaction with digital newspapers and their engagement patterns in Agra

Review of Literature

The subject of digital news consumption behavior has been examined by numerous scholars seeking to comprehend the evolving patterns in how audiences engage with news content in the digital age. Researchers have investigated how the advent of internet-connected mobile devices and social media platforms have transformed how individuals access and interact with journalistic information. This work aims to provide media organizations and policymakers insight into evolving consumer preferences and habits to effectively serve and reach audiences in the increasingly digital news landscape.

(Šmahel, 2016) found that approximately one-fifth of Czech Internet users regularly participate in online communities, with no significant gender differences in membership levels. Younger age groups tend to be the most active participants. The study examined the correlation between engagement in online communities and the quality of users' offline social lives. It also explored the perceived psychological benefits of belonging to an online group.

(Oweis & Khoury, 2014) Indicated the adoption and adaptation of new technologies by three Lebanese online newspapers: Anhalonline, Aldiyaronline, and Elantra. Ethnographic observations, interviews, and qualitative and quantitative content analysis were employed. Diffusion of Innovation theory revealed the newspapers remained in the 'trial stage' for an extended period. Factors like the political/economic situation, global technology flow, media industry competition, Lebanese Diaspora, Arab revolts, and social media influenced slow development. Editors fell between 'late majority' and 'laggards' in adopting online technologies. Lebanese online newspapers tended to follow print news delivery, undervaluing interactive features.

(Thurman & Fletcher, 2019) discussed that the time spent engaging with newspaper publishers declined by 40% despite the accessibility and affordability of digital platforms. The youngest age group saw the most substantial proportional decrease in time spent while the oldest age group saw the smallest. Variations in impact occurred among individual newspaper brands and can be attributed to differences in their multiplatform approaches. While digital distribution did not meaningfully alter preexisting age group trends, it did help facilitate changes in media consumption habits and affected the attention paid to newspapers.

(Gooding, 2016) found that users view the title page more than any other by a large margin. This is likely to reflect the way that the formal significance of the front page has been strengthened by the browsing interface: users accessing newspapers by browsing,

for instance, will be taken to the title page by default, with no guarantee that they will browse further pages in the edition.

(Kim, Park, Kim, Park, & Cho, 2018) Assessing the accuracy of articles with three grade scales showed that the percentage with high accuracy was 38.9%, 47.2%, and 23.3%. Assessment of reliability scores for five selected articles in each group showed that there were statistically significant differences between common readers and dermatologists ($p < 0.05$).

(Taipale & Sakari, 2013) focused on how Internet use displaces printed newspaper reading, particularly among male respondents. Women tend to read more printed newspapers as they spend more time on the Internet, aligning with the efficacy hypothesis. Men, however, read more online newspapers than women.

Methodology

Type of Research

This study aimed to conduct large-scale structured data collection to examine the key factors influencing the preference for digital newspapers in Agra, India. Quantitative descriptive research methods were utilized, including statistical analysis of survey responses and questionnaires distributed to participants. The findings seek to provide valuable insights into the consumption of news in digital versus print formats within the specified community.

Data Collection Sources

To gain a comprehensive perspective on the digital landscape and recognize the central aspects impacting consumer preference for digital newspapers in Agra, it was considered essential to employ a diligent methodology toward primary data collection. To accomplish this objective, structured survey instruments and questionnaires were utilized as the primary means of data collection.

Data Analysis Tools

The study being conducted in Agra utilized various statistical techniques to analyze collected data and draw meaningful insights. Descriptive statistics was employed to summarize and describe the basic features of the data. This formed the foundation for further exploration and help identify patterns. Hypothesis testing through the chi-square test and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was also integral to the research methodology. The chi-square test is a nonparametric method used for comparing observed data with data we would expect to obtain according to a specific hypothesis. CFA, meanwhile, is a statistical technique for testing how well-measured variables represent constructs. Together, these analytical approaches should aid in uncovering trends within the data, determining correlations, and validating or rejecting proposed hypotheses. The application of such quantitative methods promised to yield valuable findings for this study in Agra.

Variable Measurement

To thoroughly examine the factors influencing the preference for digital newspapers in Agra, a carefully selected sample size of 100 students was chosen for this study. The sample size was chosen to strike a compromise between statistical importance and practical efficiency. The study's sample size of 118 attempts to provide a representative glimpse of the varied viewpoints and experiences within newspaper consumption regarding the incorporation of digital platforms. This sample size is regarded as adequate to capture an in-depth understanding ensuring that the findings are reliable. The source of data for this study was a questionnaire. In the questionnaire, there are students as respondents who provide responses or answers to the questions asked. Google Form questionnaires are intended to conduct a study to find out something and to understand the opinion of the instructions given

The independent and dependent variables were measured as follows:

1. Digital Newspapers Exposure: Several items in the questionnaire were used to measure the exposure pattern of respondents to different platforms on both mainstream media and digital media. Respondents were asked the following questions on a Likert scale "You prefer accessing digital newspapers on a smartphone or computer." and were provided with the following responses (1 = Strongly Agree, 2 = Agree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Disagree, 5 = Strongly Disagree); "Your comfort with technology influence your digital newspaper choice." and were provided with the following responses (1 = Strongly Agree,

2 = Agree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Disagree, 5 = Strongly Disagree). The frequency of respondents' digital newspaper use was also measured by asking them how often they access news and information from both mainstream and digital media. Response categories ranged from (1 =Daily; 2 =Several times a week ; 3 =Once a week ; 4 =Occasionally; 5 = Rarely)

2. Customer Satisfaction: To measure the level of customer satisfaction while using digital newspapers, respondents were first asked "How satisfied are you with the timeliness of updates on your preferred digital newspaper platform?" and were provided with the following responses (1 = Extremely Satisfied; 2 = Satisfied ; 3 = Neutral; 4 = Dissatisfied; 5 = Extremely Dissatisfied). The respondents were then asked "Overall, how satisfied are you with your experience with digital newspapers?" with responses ranging from (1 being highly dissatisfied and 5 being highly satisfied).

3. Engagement Patterns: To measure the type of information respondents prefer to access on digital newspapers, they were first asked "What type of information do they usually access on digital newspapers?" Response options, which respondents were asked to choose as many as applied to them, are News Articles, Opinion Pieces and Editorials, Visual Content (Images, Infographics), Interactive Content (Quizzes, Polls), Long-Form Features and In-Depth Analysis, User-Generated Content (Comments, Discussions). The respondents were then asked about "their average daily time spent on their preferred digital newspaper platform." Response options, which respondents were asked to choose as many as applied to them, are Less than 15 minutes, 15 to 30 minutes, 30 minutes to 1 hour, 1 to 2 hours, and More than 2 hours.)

4. Perception of Information Accessibility: Several items in the questionnaire were used to measure the perception of information accessibility in digital newspapers by the consumer. Respondents were asked the following questions: "How easy is it for you to find specific information in digital newspapers?" and were provided with the following responses (1 = Very Easy; 2 = Easy ;3 = Neutral; 4 = Difficult; 5 = Very Difficult). The respondents were then asked "How do you perceive the accessibility of information in digital newspapers?" were provided with the following responses (1 =Excellent; 2 = Very Good; 3 = Good; 4 = Fair; 5 = Poor).

Sampling

Sample Frame

The sample frame for this study has been carefully constructed to ensure a wide range of respondents are included. A variety of viewpoints on consumers' newspaper preferences was collected through the administration of questionnaires. These surveys gathered perspectives from demographically diverse participants. Statistical analysis was then performed on the results to identify trends in readership habits and sections of interest. By casting a wide net with the sampling approach and collecting both qualitative and quantitative data, this research aimed to provide nuanced insights into how different demographic groups engage with newspapers. The findings will help publications better understand the needs and preferences of their audiences so they can tailor content and layouts accordingly. A robust methodology, incorporating mixed methods, seeks to deliver results that offer meaningful takeaways for both academics and industry professionals.

Sample Size

The sample size was chosen with the goal of balancing statistical significance and practical feasibility. This study aimed to recruit a sample of 100 participants to achieve a representative view of the diverse range of perspectives and experiences within the city of Agra. While a larger sample size may further enhance statistical power, practical constraints including time, resources, and accessibility require setting reasonable boundaries. It is believed that surveying 100 individuals will generate broadly generalized insights into attitudes across demographics in Agra while respecting fiscal and time limitations. The chosen sample size of 100 seeks a midpoint between the competing priorities of significance and efficiency.

Sampling Technique

For this study, the research employed a judgmental sampling strategy. This approach involves the researcher using their expertise and knowledge to select a group of participants from the wider population who can best inform the research questions. Through the experience and perspectives, these targeted individuals will provide valuable insights that align well with the focus and scope of the project. By leveraging the researcher's discretion and evaluation of each potential participant's relevance and qualifications, this sampling method aims to yield data from the most well-suited and informative sample rather than a randomly selected group. The researcher judges that this allows for the collection of the most robust and applicable information to support meaningful analysis and conclusions related to the topic under examination.

Tools Used Questionnaires

Statistics Used in the Study Confirmatory Factor Analysis and Chi-Square Test was used in this study.

Result and Discussion The following were the demographical findings from the responses received through the questionnaire :

Gender Count

Gender

118 responses

Figure 1. Variation of gender in the data collected

In Figure 1, Based on the results of the questionnaire, the respondents were 37.3% males and 62.7% females.

Age Count

Figure 2. Variation of age in the data collected

In Figure 2, based on the results of the questionnaire, the respondents were 1.7% of age less than 15 years, 37.3% of age 15-20 years, 44.1% of age 20-25 years, 8.5% of age 25-35 years, 2.5% of age 30-45 years, 4.2% of age 45-55 years and 1.7% of age above 55 years.

Level of Education

Figure 3. Variation of the level of education in the data collected

In Figure 3, based on the results of the questionnaire, the respondents were 20.3% high school students, 58.5% undergraduates, 11.9% post-graduates, 3.4% Ph.D. students, 2.5% with professional certifications and the remaining 3% with other courses

Marital Status

Figure 4. Variation of marital status in the data collected

In Figure 4, based on the results of the questionnaire, the respondents were 14.4% married and 85.6% unmarried

Satisfaction Level With Digital Newspapers

Figure 5. Level of Satisfaction of the Customers with Digital Newspapers

In Figure 5, based on the results of the questionnaire, 4.2% of respondents were highly dissatisfied, 10.2% were dissatisfied, 30.5% were neutral, 31.4% were satisfied and 23.7% were highly satisfied.

Type of Content Consumed by Digital Newspaper Readers

Figure 6. Engagement Patterns of Digital Newspaper Readers

In Figure 6, based on the results of the questionnaire, 70.3% of respondents preferred consuming news articles, 39.8% preferred opinion pieces and editorials, 56.8% preferred visual content (images, infographics), 42.4% preferred interactive content (quizzes, polls), 31.4% preferred long-form features and in-depth analysis and remaining 25.4% preferred user-generated content (comments, discussions).

Hypothesis Testing

The chi-square test was conducted to analyze survey response data, using a significance level of 0.05. Observed frequencies were collected through a

questionnaire, while expected frequencies were calculated using Microsoft Excel. The chi-square test was performed in Excel and produced the following results for the respective hypothesis.

H₀₁: Convenience has no significant impact on the digital newspaper preference

H_{a1}: Convenience has a significant impact on the digital newspaper preference

Observed Frequency

Newspapers	Agree	Disagree	Neutral	Strongly	Strongly	Grand Total
				Agree	Disagree	
Both	22	1	6	5	0	34
Digital Newspapers	29	0	5	23	0	57
Printed Newspapers	8	6	6	2	1	23
Grand Total	59	7	17	30	1	114

Expected Frequency

Newspapers	Agree	Disagree	Neutral	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Grand Total
Both	17.59649	2.087719	5.070175	8.947368421	0.298245614	34
Digital Newspapers	29.5	3.5	8.5	15	0.5	57
Printed Newspapers	11.90351	1.412281	3.429825	6.052631579	0.201754386	23
Grand Total	59	7	17	30	1	114

Contingency Table

Observed	Expected	Observed -Expected	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² /E
22	17.60	4.40	19.39	1.10
1	2.09	-1.09	1.18	0.57
6	5.07	0.93	0.86	0.17
5	8.95	-3.95	15.58	1.74
0	0.30	-0.30	0.09	0.30
29	29.50	-0.50	0.25	0.01
0	3.50	-3.50	12.25	3.50
5	8.50	-3.50	12.25	1.44
23	15.00	8.00	64.00	4.27
0	0.50	-0.50	0.25	0.50
8	11.90	-3.90	15.24	1.28
6	1.41	4.59	21.05	14.90
6	3.43	2.57	6.61	1.93
2	6.05	-4.05	16.42	2.71

1	0.20	0.80	0.64	3.16
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i. Calculated chi-square value: 37.576061

ii. P-value: 9.01456E-06

iii. Degrees of freedom: 8

iv. Critical chi-square value: 15.507

These results indicate that there is a statistically significant difference between the observed and expected response frequencies at the 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$). Also, the calculated chi-square value exceeds the critical value of the chi-square test. Therefore, The null hypothesis that the response distribution occurred by chance can be rejected

H₀₂: Age has no significant impact on digital newspaper preference

H_{a2}: Age has a significant impact on digital newspaper preference

Observed Frequency

Age Group	Agree	Disagree	Neutral	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Grand Total
15-20 years	27	1	7	9	0	44
20-25 years	20	4	9	16	0	49
25-35 years	5	0	1	3	1	10
35-45 years	1	2	0	0	0	3
45-55 years	4	0	0	1	0	5
55+ years	0	0	0	1	0	1
Less than 15 years	2	0	0	0	0	2
Grand Total	59	7	17	30	1	114

Expected Frequency

Age Group	Agree	Disagree	Neutral	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Grand Total
15-20 years	22.77192982	2.701754	6.561404	11.57894737	0.385964912	44
20-25 years	25.35964912	3.008772	7.307018	12.89473684	0.429824561	49
25-35 years	5.175438596	0.614035	1.491228	2.631578947	0.087719298	10
35-45 years	1.552631579	0.184211	0.447368	0.789473684	0.026315789	3
45-55 years	2.587719298	0.307018	0.745614	1.315789474	0.043859649	5
55+ years	0.51754386	0.061404	0.149123	0.263157895	0.00877193	1
Less than 15 years	1.035087719	0.122807	0.298246	0.526315789	0.01754386	2
Grand Total	59	7	17	30	1	114

Contingency Table

Observed	Expected	Observed-Expected	(O-B) ²	(O-B) ² /E
27	22.7719298	4.22807	17.88	0.79
1	2.70175439	-1.70175	2.90	1.07
7	6.56140351	0.438596	0.19	0.03
9	11.5789474	-2.57895	6.65	0.57
0	0.38596491	-0.38596	0.15	0.39
20	25.3596491	-5.35965	28.73	1.13
4	3.00877193	0.991228	0.98	0.33
9	7.30701754	1.692982	2.87	0.39
16	12.8947368	3.105263	9.64	0.75

0	0.42982456	-0.42982	0.18	0.43
5	5.1754386	-0.17544	0.03	0.01
0	0.61403509	-0.61404	0.38	0.61
1	1.49122807	-0.49123	0.24	0.16
3	2.63157895	0.368421	0.14	0.05
1	0.0877193	0.912281	0.83	9.49
1	1.55263158	-0.55263	0.31	0.20
2	0.18421053	1.815789	3.30	17.90
0	0.44736842	-0.44737	0.20	0.45
0	0.78947368	-0.78947	0.62	0.79
0	0.02631579	-0.02632	0.00	0.03
4	2.5877193	1.412281	1.99	0.77
0	0.30701754	-0.30702	0.09	0.31
0	0.74561404	-0.74561	0.56	0.75
1	1.31578947	-0.31579	0.10	0.08
0	0.04385965	-0.04386	0.00	0.04
0	0.51754386	-0.51754	0.27	0.52
0	0.06140351	-0.0614	0.00	0.06
0	0.14912281	-0.14912	0.02	0.15
1	0.26315789	0.736842	0.54	2.06
0	0.00877193	-0.00877	0.00	0.01
2	1.03508772	0.964912	0.93	0.90
0	0.12280702	-0.12281	0.02	0.12
0	0.29824561	-0.29825	0.09	0.30
0	0.52631579	-0.52632	0.28	0.53
0	0.01754386	-0.01754	0.00	0.02

i. Calculated chi-square value: 42.16

ii. P-value: 0.012373931

iii. Degrees of freedom: 24

iv. Critical chi-square value: 36.415

These results indicate that there is a statistically significant difference between the observed and expected response frequencies at the 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$). Also, the calculated chi-square value exceeds the critical value of the chi-square test. Therefore, The null hypothesis that the response distribution occurred by chance can be rejected.

H₀₃: Consumer awareness of the environment has no significant impact on digital newspaper preference.

H_{a3}: Consumer awareness of the environment has a significant impact on digital newspaper preference.

Observed Frequency

Newspapers	Agree	Disagree	Neutral	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Grand Total
Both	13	0	5	4	1	23
Digital Newspapers	42	4	9	24	0	79
Printed Newspapers	4	3	3	2	0	12
Grand Total	59	7	17	30	1	114

Expected Frequency

NEWSPAPERS	Agree	Disagree	Neutral	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Grand Total
Both	11.90351	1.412281	3.429825	6.052631579	0.201754386	23
Digital Newspapers	40.88596	4.850877	11.7807	20.78947368	0.692982456	79
Printed Newspapers	6.210526	0.736842	1.789474	3.157894737	0.105263158	12
Grand Total	59	7	17	30	1	114

Contingency Table

Observed	Expected	Observed-Expected	(O-B) ²	(O-B) ² /E
13	11.9035088	1.096491	1.202293	0.1010032
0	1.4122807	-1.41228	1.994537	1.4122807
5	3.42982456	1.570175	2.465451	0.7188271
4	6.05263158	-2.05263	4.213296	0.6961098
1	0.20175439	0.798246	0.637196	3.1582761
42	40.8859649	1.114035	1.241074	0.0303545
4	4.85087719	-0.85088	0.723992	0.1492497
9	11.7807018	-2.7807	7.732302	0.6563533
24	20.7894737	3.210526	10.30748	0.4958028
0	0.69298246	-0.69298	0.480225	0.6929825
4	6.21052632	-2.21053	4.886427	0.7867975
3	0.73684211	2.263158	5.121884	6.9511278
3	1.78947368	1.210526	1.465374	0.8188854
2	3.15789474	-1.15789	1.34072	0.4245614
0	0.10526316	-0.10526	0.01108	0.1052632

- i. Calculated chi-square value: 17.197875
- ii. P-value: 0.028113323
- iii. Degrees of freedom: 8
- iv. Critical chi-square value: 17.19787513

These results indicate that there is a statistically significant difference between the observed and expected response frequencies at the 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$). Also, the calculated chi-square value exceeds the critical value of the chi-square test. Therefore, The null hypothesis that the response distribution occurred by chance can be rejected.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

A confirmatory factor analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS statistical software to test the underlying theoretical factor structure of the measurement scales employed in the study. The confirmatory factor analysis provided support for utilizing a measurement model that is consistent with the conceptual framework guiding the research. Overall, the confirmatory factor analysis confirmed the suitability of proceeding with the defined scales to explore the research questions and hypotheses put forth regarding the nature of the relationships between variables within the study's conceptual model.

The total variance table demonstrates how variance is distributed among 28 potential factors. Four Factors have eigenvalues exceeding one, which is a typical threshold for a factor to be considered meaningful. It can be concluded that these four factors extracted from all the variables explain about 59.878 % variance of the total variance.

Component	Total Variance Explained								
	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.621	24.323	24.323	4.621	24.323	24.323	4.174	21.969	21.969
2	3.357	17.671	41.994	3.357	17.671	41.994	3.041	16.004	37.973
3	1.713	9.014	51.008	1.713	9.014	51.008	2.192	11.538	49.510
4	1.685	8.869	59.878	1.685	8.869	59.878	1.970	10.367	59.878
5	1.221	6.427	66.305						
6	1.141	6.003	72.308						
7	1.082	5.695	78.003						
8	.754	3.969	81.972						
9	.612	3.220	85.192						
10	.599	3.151	88.343						
11	.466	2.453	90.796						
12	.430	2.262	93.058						
13	.376	1.977	95.035						
14	.263	1.385	96.420						
15	.218	1.147	97.567						
16	.187	.982	98.549						
17	.156	.822	99.371						
18	.076	.398	99.769						
19	.044	.231	100.000						

Factors Analysed-

Through factor analysis utilizing a Rotated Component Matrix, four key factors were identified as influencing preferences for digital newspapers:

- 1. Convenience:** Digital newspapers provide enhanced convenience through portability, as the format allows reading from any location on mobile devices. Additionally, digital newspapers offer storage-related convenience as back issues consume minimal physical space. The lack of production and distribution costs associated with digital newspapers enhances economic convenience for readers.
- 2. Comfort with Technology:** Some readers find digital newspapers more comfortable to use given the ability to easily navigate pages and customizable presentation styles. The on-screen format allows simple scrolling or swiping between articles and sections.
- 3. Ease of Accessing Information:** Readers noted digital newspapers simplify accessing breaking news stories and locating specific details as search functions can

rapidly scan content. Additionally, the constant connectivity of digital formats ensures timely updates are immediately available.

4. Wide Range of Sources: A significant advantage of digital newspapers is the vast array of additional sources and perspectives included beyond any single publication. Readers have access to a true plethora of local, national, and global news sources simultaneously from a single online platform or app.

Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Analysis

A Cronbach's alpha reliability analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS statistical software to evaluate the internal consistency of the measurement instrument employed in this study. The measurement instrument comprised 10 items designed to assess constructs related to organizational culture. The reliability analysis resulted in a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.787, indicating good internal consistency among the items on the measurement instrument. A Cronbach's alpha value of 0.7 or higher is generally considered acceptable in most social science research. Therefore, based on the results of this analysis, it can be concluded that the measurement instrument demonstrated good reliability and was deemed appropriate for use in measuring organizational culture as part of this research study.

Implications of The Research

1. Younger generations currently make up the majority of online news consumers. However, efforts should be made to expand accessibility to other age groups as well. Streamlining content delivery and simplifying user experiences could help engage older audiences

2. While digital newspapers now exist, the average time spent engaging with news applications remains low, under 30 minutes for most. Captivating and engaging content presentations and optimizing user retention should be a design priority. Maintaining readership interest levels promotes regular consumption.

3. Current advertising-driven business models may inadvertently undermine the user experience. As platforms aim to expand audiences and engagement, new revenue streams merit consideration. Prioritizing reader needs over advertisements could strengthen brand affinity and allow quality journalism to take center stage. Multiple avenues exist to monetize loyal, content-driven communities in sustainable ways.

Conclusion

Emerging realities within the media business, especially the newspaper, show that the paradigm is shifting. Newspaper reading is no longer classified as being a physical activity thanks to the growth of online news mediums. Nowadays the mode of reading newspapers is changed from print media to online newspapers in mobile apps and thus has had an impact on the way people consume news as well.

With the coming of the online newspaper, the offline newspaper seems to be losing its hegemony. Although both versions of newspapers still possess unique features or attributes that endear them to their respective readers. However, as more readers appear to go online, questions about the role of content as a determinant of newspaper choice naturally arise, especially now that publishers earnestly seek a better business model to save the already troubled print industry. In this regard, while preferred content slightly differs across the board, for many, content does not necessarily determine whether they read online or hardcopy, rather, availability and certain demographic and psychographic factors do. Again, even though the online version may have a little advantage over the hardcopy version, a small percentage of readers will always choose hardcopy newspapers. Therefore, it may continue to be a combination of print and online journalism for the foreseeable future, with online possibly replacing offline with time.

Limitation of the Study

1) The study's limited sample size or focus on a specific educational setting may restrict the generalizability of its findings. A larger, more diverse sample would offer a more comprehensive understanding of the factors' effects across different populations and educational environments.

2) The study's measurement and control of variables, such as convenience and age, may have been limited and subjective, potentially not fully capturing their complexity. Additionally, uncontrolled variables could have influenced the outcomes, affecting the reliability and validity of the results.

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